

TABLE I—ARYLAZO-BIS-ACETOXIME COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Aryl	Colour, shape of crystals	M.p.	Analysis % : Found/Calcd.*			Colour with α -naphthylamine
				C	H	N	
1.	<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	Reddish brown, tiny	119°	59.10 (59.07)	7.48 (7.63)	20.63 (21.19)	Reddish brown colour on warming and then cooling
2.	<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenyl	White silky, flakes	102°	53.32 (53.05)	6.03 (6.16)	18.76 (19.03)	No action. Test not given
3.	<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenyl	Light reddish brown, tiny	174°	52.88 (53.05)	6.10 (6.16)	18.91 (19.03)	No change in colour. Test not given
4.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenyl	Light brown, fine	140°	53.17 (53.05)	5.90 (6.16)	18.68 (19.03)	No change in colour. Test not given
5.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellow, large rectangular	48°	48.64 (48.80)	5.66 (5.80)	23.61 (23.72)	Light pink colour on gentle warming
6.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	Light brown, needless	50°	48.69 (48.80)	5.72 (5.80)	23.60 (23.72)	Pink colour on warming
7.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellow, needless	69°	48.94 (48.80)	5.69 (5.80)	23.43 (23.72)	Pink colour on warming
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl ^a	Brown, fine	111°	51.18 (50.62)	5.95 (6.02)	19.40 (19.68)	Violet red colour on slight warming
9.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl ^b	Dark violet red, small	111°	50.41 (50.62)	5.98 (6.02)	19.52 (19.68)	Immediate pink colour in cold, intensified on heating
10.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl ^c	Black, needles	113°	50.13 (50.61)	5.99 (6.02)	19.21 (19.68)	Immediate pink colour in cold, intensified on heating.
11.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl ^d	Yellow, needles	144°	43.61 (43.78)	5.39 (5.20)	17.61 (17.02)	Red colour on slight warming
12.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Violet, tiny	98°	55.89 (55.70)	7.28 (7.19)	19.66 (19.99)	Reddish brown colour on warming
13.	<i>m</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Blackish brown, fine	103°	55.56 (55.70)	6.87 (7.19)	19.63 (19.99)	Reddish brown colour on warming
14.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Shining brown, tiny	139°	55.81 (55.70)	7.02 (7.19)	19.75 (19.99)	Reddish brown colour on warming

*Halogen % : ^aCl, 12.04 (12.44) ; ^bCl, 12.67 (12.44) ; ^cCl, 12.13 (12.44) ; ^dBr, 23.82 (24.27).

It has been observed that arylazo-bis-acetoximes do not give spot tests with picric acid but give a positive spot test with α -naphthylamine. This may be indicative of a greater contribution of hydroxy-triazene form (I) towards the final structure. The negative picric acid test can also be interpreted to mean that the contribution of triazene-oxide form (II) is either altogether absent or is negligible and that arylazo-bis-acetoximes might be existing predominantly in form I.

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Raney Nickel Desulphuration of Cyclic Nitrogen and Sulphur containing Compounds. Desulphuration of 1,2,4-Thiadiazolidines

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RECENTLY, we have carried out the desulphuration studies of certain acyclic thioamido group containing compounds^{1,2} in the presence of Raney nickel (W-2). The present paper describes the Raney nickel desulphuration of certain cyclic thioamido group containing system.

When 5-imino-4-phenyl-3-phenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (1a) was desulphurated in boiling ethanolic medium in the presence of Raney nickel (W-2), a pale yellow solution was produced. This on removing the solvent, afforded a solid crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 150°. This product neither reduced Fehling's solution nor Tollen's reagent. It formed a hydrochloride, m.p. 137° and a picrate, m.p. 170° by its interaction with cold concentrated HCl and aqueous picric acid, respectively. On reaction with phenyl isothiocyanate it produced 1-(*N, N'*-diphenyl)formamidino-3-phenylthiourea (3a), m. p. 165-66° (Scheme 1).

where, R = a, phenyl; b, *p*-tolyl, c, *o*-tolyl; d, *m*-tolyl, e, *p*-chlorophenyl, f, *m*-chlorophenyl, and g, *p*-anisyl.

Scheme 1

On the basis of all the above facts, the product with m.p. 150° was identified as 1,3-diphenylguanidine (2). Its identity was also confirmed through its undepressed m.m.p. with authentic sample and superimposable IR spectra. The desulphuration of 1a in boiling benzene medium also afforded 1,3-diphenylguanidine (2a).

the corresponding 1,3-diarylguanidines (2b-g) and the latter on reaction with phenyl isothiocyanate produced 1-(*N,N'*-diaryl)formamidino-3-phenylthioureas (3a-g) (Table 2).

Experimental

Raney nickel was prepared as usual⁸. The required phenyl isothiocyanate was prepared by the oxidative decomposition of ammonium phenylthiocarbamate⁴ in the presence of lead nitrate. 1-Arylthioureas were prepared by the interaction of ammonium thiocyanate and arylamine hydrochloride⁵. The so-called Hector's bases were prepared according to the procedure described earlier⁶, viz. by the oxidation of an appropriate arylthioureas with hydrogen peroxide followed by basification with dilute ammonium hydroxide.

Desulphuration of 1,2,4-thiadiazolidines (1). Formation of 1,3-diarylguanidines (2): Details of a

TABLE 1—4-ARYL-3-ARYLIMINO-5-IMINO-1,2,4-THIADIAZOLIDINES (1)

Compd. no.	1-Arylthiourea (g)	1 (g) m.p. °C	Analy: % Found/(Calcd)	
			N	S
1a	Phenyl (7.6)	4-Phenyl-3-phenylimino (4.7), 182	21.23 (20.89)	11.72 (11.94)
b	<i>p</i> -Tolyl (8.3)	4- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylimino (5.4), 132	19.19 (18.91)	10.63 (10.81)
c	<i>o</i> -Tolyl (8.3)	4- <i>o</i> -Tolyl-3- <i>o</i> -tolylimino (5.0), 175	19.32 (18.91)	10.38 (10.81)
d*	<i>m</i> -Tolyl (8.3)	4- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-3- <i>m</i> -tolylimino (4.8), 110	19.25 (18.91)	10.57 (10.81)
e*	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl (9.3)	4- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-3- <i>p</i> -chlorophenylimino (5.6), 159	17.05 (16.61)	9.27 (9.49)
f*	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl (9.3)	4- <i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl-3- <i>m</i> -chlorophenylimino (5.5), 172	16.82 (16.61)	9.16 (9.49)
g*	<i>p</i> -Anisyl (9.1)	4- <i>p</i> -Anisyl-3- <i>p</i> -anisylimino (4.5), 75	17.28 (17.07)	9.43 (9.76)

* Prepared for the first time.

TABLE 2—RANEY NICKEL DESULPHURATION OF SOME 4-ARYL-3-ARYLIMINO-5-IMINO-1,2,4-THIADIAZOLIDINES (1)

Sl. no.	Aryl substituent	1,2,4-Thiadiazolidine (1) (g)*	Product				Hydrochloride M.p. °C	Picrate M.p. °C	Amidinothiourea (3) M.p. °C	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)	
			Diarylguanidine (2) (g)	Yield %	N %: Found/(Calcd.)	M.p. °C				N	S
1.	Phenyl	1a (5.4)	2a (3.4)	150	80	19.65 (19.90)	138	3a 165	16.35 (16.18)	9.05 (9.25)	
2.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	1b (5.9)	2b (3.9)	173	81	17.28 (17.57)	100	3b 137	14.49 (14.97)	8.23 (8.55)	
3.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	1c (5.9)	2c (3.7)	179	78	17.72 (17.57)	184	3c 175	14.72 (14.97)	8.33 (8.55)	
4.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	1d (5.9)	2d (3.6)	110	76	17.09 (17.57)	160	3d 139	15.05 (14.97)	8.07 (8.55)	
5.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	1e (6.7)	2e (4.5)	138	80	14.46 (15.00)	180	3e 137	13.52 (13.49)	7.58 (7.71)	
6.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	1f (6.7)	2f (4.3)	141	76	15.23 (15.00)	200	3f 135	13.42 (13.49)	7.29 (7.71)	
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	1g (6.6)	2g (4.1)	158	75	15.49 (15.50)	195	3g 132	13.97 (13.79)	7.53 (7.88)	

* 1 and Raney nickel taken in 1 : 5 ratio. Satisfactory C and H analyses obtained in all cases.

All the other 4-aryl-3-arylimino-5-imino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines (1b-g) on Raney nickel desulphuration in both ethanolic and benzene media afforded

typical desulphuration reaction of the 1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (1a) are as follows. A suspension of 1a (5.4 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (50.0 ml) was added to a

suspension of Raney nickel (W-2 ; 27.0 g) in ethanol (100.0 ml) and the resulting mixture was refluxed with constant stirring for 150 min. The used-up Raney nickel was removed by hot filtration. The solvent was distilled out from the filtrate, and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to yield the product (2a) (3.4 g, 80%), m.p. 150° (Found : N, 19.65. Req'd. for $C_{15}H_{15}N_3$: N, 19.90%); ν_{max} 3 375 (NH), 1 635 (C=N), 1 372 (Ar), 1 295 (C-N) and 1 070 cm^{-1} (Ar-Cl)⁷⁻⁹; δ 7.05-7.40 (ArH); 2a afforded a hydrochloride when treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid, m.p. 138° (Found : Eq. wt., 240.8. Req'd. for $C_{15}H_{15}N_3 \cdot HCl$: Eq. wt., 247.5); its ethanolic solution when mixed with aqueous picric acid gave a picrate, m.p. 170° (Found : N, 19.39. Req'd. for $C_{15}H_{15}N_3 \cdot C_6H_3N_3O_7$: N, 19.09%).

Formation of 3a : To a solution of 2a (0.5 g) in ethanol (25.0 ml) phenyl isothiocyanate (0.5 ml) was added, and the mixture refluxed for 150 min. The solvent was then removed by distillation and 1-(N, N'-diphenyl) formamidino-3-phenylthiourea (3a) crystallised from ethanol (0.7 g), m.p. 165° (Found : N, 16.35 ; S, 9.05. Req'd. for $C_{20}H_{19}N_4S$: N, 6.18 ; S, 9.25%); ν_{max} 3 370 (NH), 1 550 (C=N) 1 370 (Ar) and 1 300 cm^{-1} (C-N); δ 6.69-6.93 (ArH).

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Isolation of 16-Hentriacontanone, Alcohols and Sterols from the Leaves of *Annona squamosa*

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THE leaves of *Annona squamosa* (Annonaceae) commonly known as Sarifah, are widely used as anthelmintic and also for other ailments¹. They contain an acrid principle fatal to insects² and used to kill lice³. The alcoholic extract of the leaves is reported to have anticancer⁴ activity. The survey of literature revealed that no other work, except the isolation of alkaloids^{4,5} and essential oils⁶ from the leaves has so far been carried out. The present note deals with the chemical examination of petroleum ether extractives of the leaves of this plant.

The air dried leaves of *A. squamosa* collected from the surroundings of Aligarh were extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). The unsaponifiable fraction on column chromatography over silica gel was separated into three fractions.

Ketone : This fraction was obtained on elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) and purified with methanol as white amorphous powder, m.p. 83-84°; R_f 0.90 and ν_{max} 1 700 cm^{-1} (ketone). Gc-mass over OV-17 showed the single peak having molecular ion peak at m/e 450 and other peaks at m/e 254 and 239. It was identified 16-hentriacontanone on the above basis and by preparing its oxime, m.p. 57-58°.

Alcohols : This fraction was obtained on elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (2 : 3) and purification from methanol as white solid, m.p. 85-86°; R_f 0.40 ; ν_{max} 1 070 and 3 200 cm^{-1} . Glc analysis over SE-30 represented it to be mixture of a homologous series of aliphatic alcohols with maximum participation of n-hexacosanol (C_{26} , 39%), n-octacosanol (C_{28} , 36%) and n-triacontanol (C_{30} , 19%) along with other homologues in small quantities. Even-carbon number alkanols⁷ were dominated.

Sterols : This fraction was obtained on further elution of the column with benzene and purified with methanol. It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test and R_f 0.15. Its acetyl derivative was found to be a mixture of 24-methylcholest-5-ene-3 β -ol (campesterol), 24-ethylcholesta-5, 22-diene-3 β -ol (stigmasterol) and 24-ethylcholest-5-ene-3 β -ol (β -sitosterol) identified as acetate on the basis of co-argentation tlc. The major product, sitosteryl acetate was separated from the plate and was identified on the basis of co-tlc and m. m. p. The acetyl derivative on glc analysis over OV-17 confirmed the presence of campesterol (RRt=1.31, 28.6%), stigmasterol (RRt=1.42, 4.6%) and β -sitosterol (RRt=